

Kieler Ostrechts-Notizen

Кильский журнал Восточноевропейского права

Kiel Journal of East European Law

Hrsg. vom Institut für Osteuropäisches Recht der Universität Kiel

Themenheft

Rechtliche Aspekte der Eingliederung der Halbinsel Krim in die Russische Föderation im Jahr 2014

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Editorial

Liebe Leserinnen und Leser,

diese Ausgabe der Kieler Ostrechts-Notizen erscheint in der Zeit der tiefsten Krise der politischen Beziehungen zwischen Russland und den Staaten des Westens seit dem Zerfall der Sowjetunion. Im Zentrum dieser Krise stehen die politischen Entwicklungen in der Ukraine seit Herbst 2013, die in der Flucht des damaligen ukrainischen Präsidenten Janukowitsch im Februar 2014 nach Russland kulminierten. In der Folge dieser Ereignisse erklärten politische Organe der ukrainischen Halbinsel Krim im März 2014, nach einem von Russland unterstützten umstrittenen Referendum, die Unabhängigkeit der Krim von der Ukraine und unmittelbar darauf den Beitritt der Krim zur Russischen Föderation. Die EU, die USA und zahlreiche weitere Staaten werfen Russland eine völkerrechtswidrige Annexion der Krim vor und verhängen aus diesem Grund u.a. wirtschaftliche und persönliche Sanktionen.

Das vorliegende Heft will einen Beitrag dazu leisten, die Vielschichtigkeit der juristischen Dimensionen der Krim-Krise zu verdeutlichen. Im Vordergrund steht zunächst die völkerrechtliche Beurteilung der Eingliederung der Krim in die Russische Föderation. Hierzu werden in dem Heft zum einen das Gutachten einer Gruppe führender polnischer Völkerrechtswissenschaftler für den Außenminister der Republik Polen zur Krim-Thematik, zum anderen ein aus dem Russischen übersetzter Beitrag eines angesehenen russischen Völkerrechtlers (Georgij Veljaminov) abgedruckt. Den Abschluss dieses Themas bildet der als Diskussionsanregung zu verstehende Beitrag des Salzburger Völkerrechtlers und „Ostrechtlers“ Michael Geistlinger über die Zukunft der Beziehungen zwischen der EU und Russland vor dem Hintergrund der Krim-Krise bzw. des Konflikts um die Ukraine.

Während die völkerrechtliche Beurteilung der Krim-Krise in der Politik und auch in der Fachöffentlichkeit häufig thematisiert wird, werden die rechtlichen Aspekte dieser politischen Vorgänge auf der Ebene Russlands und der Ukraine nur selten untersucht. In diesem Heft werden einige grundlegende juristische Texte aus Russland und der Ukraine zu dieser Thematik in deutscher Übersetzung veröffentlicht. Wer sich mit der Krim-Krise (und dem Ukraine-Konflikt) und ihrer zu erhoffenden künftigen Lösung befasst, darf nicht auf der hohen Ebene des Völkerrechts stehen bleiben, sondern muss sich auch auf die Ebene der konkreten Lösungen von Fragen des Verwaltungsrechts, Zivilrechts oder Strafrechts begeben. In diesem Zusammenhang ist interessant, dass sowohl Russland als auch die Ukraine Sondergesetze über die Sezession bzw. Eingliederung der Krim erlassen haben, die sich auch für einen Vergleich eignen, und dass inzwischen in beiden Staaten auch Rechtsprechung hierzu vorliegt.

Allen Leserinnen und Lesern wünsche ich wieder eine anregende Lektüre.

Prof. Dr. Alexander Trunk

Impressum

Die Kieler Ostrechts-Notizen werden herausgegeben von den Mitarbeiterinnen des Instituts für Osteuropäisches Recht der Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel.
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ISSN 1439 - 7935

Schutzgebühr: 10 €

Auflage: 150 Exemplare

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Nationalization of Real Estate Property in the Temporarily Occupied Territory of Ukraine: Some Legal Aspects of Protection of Civil Rights

Anatolij V. Kostruba

Legal problems of exercising and protecting civil rights play an important role in the civil law doctrine of European countries including Ukraine. Scientists such as S.S. Alekseyev, A.S. Aleksandrov, V.P. Gribov, N.S. Kuznetsova, R.A. Maydanyk, O.V. Dzera and others have approached these issues. At the same time, Ukrainian realities of today require systemic changes in treating this issue. Thus, within the period of March – September 2014 the occupation authorities in the Crimean peninsula adopted a number of law enforcement acts in respect of nationalization of state property of Ukraine, separate legal and physical persons in favour of the new constituent entity of the Russian Federation (the Republic of Crimea, the Special Status City of Sevastopol). That is why scientific problems of application of effective methods of ownership right protection, functioning of certain mechanisms of termination of civil rights and obligations require a thorough scientific study.

1. Basic concepts relating to expropriation

For legal science the high priority is supplying the scientific content for notions that would reflect legal phenomena. Understanding a specific legal phenomenon gives the possibility to reveal its internal and necessary peculiarities and characteristics, unity and interdependence of which determine its specific features and the trend of their development¹. To resolve private law issues the author is facing requires the primary articulating the concept of nationalization in the current civil law of Ukraine within the context allied legal phenomena such as requisition and confiscation. Taking into account the etymology of the above-mentioned terms (requisition – from Latin “requisitio” – requirement; confiscation (Lat.) – collection to the treasury; nationalization – from Latin “natio” – something that belongs to people (the nation)), we shall pay attention

to the fact that their legal similarity consists in the possibility of evoking legal consequences in the form of termination of an owner's proprietary right to his property against his will, and acquiring this right by another subject – the state². Thus, all these notions have one common specific feature – the forced termination of the proprietary right of a subject, which can be defined as *expropriation* (from Lat “expropriatio” – deprivation of property).

The difference between us lies in the goal of the specific legal model of one of the above-mentioned phenomena, nature of legal consequences arising, and legal grounds of formation and arising of the above-described legal structures. Which means that the difference between them has a purely functional meaning that manifests itself in their generic features.

Besides, for *requisition* such generic features are as follows: a) the subject of expropriation: movable and immovable property; b) terms of expropriation: obligatory reasonable monetary compensation; c) goal of expropriation: requirement of the state to protect public interests under conditions of the state of emergency and martial law; d) legal ground: Decree of the President of Ukraine subject to approval of the Supreme Council of Ukraine³; e) terms of using the subject of expropriation: recoverability /possibility of physical destruction in the process of operation; f) terms of existence: exercise of a public legal personality of the state; g) form of exercising the right: single act.

In its turn, for *confiscation* they are: a) the subject of expropriation: movable and immovable property; b) terms of expropriation: gratuitousness; c) goal of expropriation: measure of punishment or

¹ Kerimov D.A. *Methodology of Law (the subject-matter, functions and problems of the philosophy of law)*, Publisher Avanta, Moscow, 2000, p.159.

² Afanasyeva Ye.N. *Requisition: a Civil and Legal Aspect*, Tomsk State University, 2009, p.30.

³ On the legal regulation of the state of emergency, the Law of Ukraine № 1550-III of March 16, 2000, Administration of the Supreme Council of Ukraine, 2000, №23, p.176.

sanction for committing a crime⁴; d) legal ground: court judgement; e) terms of using the subject of expropriation: alienation at the public bidding; f) terms of existence: exercise of a legal personality of the state; g) form of exercising the right: permanent.

For nationalization these are as follows: a) the subject of expropriation: immovable property; b) terms of expropriation: obligatory reasonable monetary compensation⁵; c) goal of expropriation: ensuring sustainable economic development in the process of establishing a new subject of international public law; d) legal ground: separate law of the state; e) terms of using the subject of expropriation: non-returnability; f) terms of existence: the process of establishing a subject of international law⁶; g) form of exercising the right: single act.

Summing up the said above, we should say that such notions as confiscation, nationalization and requisition, as well as expropriation, correlate with each other as private to general. *Confiscation, requisition or nationalization* is manifestation of *expropriation* of property depending on organizational form of their implementation.

I.V. Mingazova has the same opinion; she states that the term of “*expropriation*” has generalized meaning. It presupposes acts of the state in public interests aimed at forced seizure of property, proprietary rights and interests of private ownership with the aim of establishing the proprietary right of the state. Besides, the use of the above-mentioned term allows avoiding misunderstandings in the contents of international agreements, in which *expropriation* is considered in a broader sense than nationalization⁷.

It shall be emphasized that within a long period of time there was no such notion as “nationalization” in the world legal thought. Such legal structure appeared in view of changes in public and economic form of the Russian state in the beginning of the 20th century XX, formation of a new, socialistic understanding of laws, which envisages overall socialization of production facilities, real estate and

commodities, and excludes private ownership in general. Above all, this phenomenon did not envisage any monetary compensation. One of the first respective legal acts in Russia was Decree II of the All-Russian Congress of Councils of Workers’ and Soldiers’ Deputies “On land” of November 08, 1917, Clause I of which stated that “The ownership rights of landlords to land shall be abolished immediately without redemption ...”⁸.

II. Legal regulation of nationalization in general from the Ukrainian perspective

Today, notwithstanding social changes, the term “nationalization” is still used as a manifestation of legal tradition, with certain updates, in the theory and civil legislation of a number of countries like the Russian Federation, Republic of Kazakhstan, the Republic of Belarus and others. Although in Ukrainian legislation there is no general legal regulation for nationalization, this does not mean that a theoretical analysis of this notion in the civil law of Ukraine is inexpedient. Nationalization as the grounds for termination of the proprietary right shall be reviewed in certain aspects.

1. Aspects of international law

Firstly, mention must be made of *aspects of international law*. The legal phenomenon of nationalization is a form of the accomplishment of sovereignty of the state and is, as such, in principle confirmed by Resolution №1803 (XVII) of the General Assembly of the UN “Permanent sovereignty over natural resources” of December 14, 1962. The Resolution provides for the right of people and nations to their permanent sovereignty over their natural wealth and resources, which shall be exercised in the interests of national development and for the benefit of the peoples of the respective countries⁹. The right of a sovereign state to nationalize property results from the international law principle of respect to state sovereignty as established in Declaration on principles of international law concerning friendly relationships and cooperation between state in compliance with the UN Charter (adopted by the Resolution of the General Assembly of the UN № 2625 (XXV) of October 24, 1970)¹⁰.

⁴ Civil Code of Ukraine (as of May 1, 2014), Administration of the Supreme Council of Ukraine – 2003, № 40-44, p.356 (as amended).

⁵ Permanent sovereignty over natural resources: Resolution (XVII) of the General Assembly of the UN №1803 of December 14, 1962// http://zakon4.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_819.

⁶ Permanent sovereignty over natural resources: Resolution (XVII) of the General Assembly of the UN №1803 of December 14, 1962, http://zakon4.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_819.

⁷ I.V. Mingazova, *Ownership right in international law*, Wolters Kluwer, Moscow 2007, p.35.

⁸ Dorofeyeva Yu.A. Nationalization: international private law issues, in: Samara State Academy of Economics 2000, p.34-63.

⁹ Permanent sovereignty over natural resources: Resolution (XVII) of the General Assembly of the UN №1803 of December 14, 1962, http://zakon4.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_819.

¹⁰ Declaration on principles of international law concerning friendly relations and cooperation be-

From this perspective, the right to nationalization is connected with sovereignty of a state that correlate with the issue of recognition of a State as a subject of international public law. And this does make sense as formation of a new state presupposes entrenchment of its material resources (including natural ones), which form the benefit of its people and serve as a foundation for further development of a new state. This means that nationalization is a legal phenomenon of international public law.

It shall be mentioned that within the context of the stated above, there are two approaches in the international public law theory: the *constitutive* and the *declarative* approach. According to the first approach, only the recognition of a State entails the international legal personality of a state transforming its factual status into a legal one. The declarative theory proceeds from the fact that the State acquires legal personality in view of the very fact of its formation irrespective of its recognition¹¹.

Within the context of our study, the outlined above problematics has an applied significance. It consists in the fact that constructivity of the mechanism of termination of the property right depends on one or another concept of recognizing a state as a subject of international law. Thus, in the first case, with the official recognition of a state available, the state becomes a subject of respective legal relationships, particularly, it acquires legal personality as regards nationalization of property of the previous state-owner. This gives this process an additional political burden, makes the mechanism of termination of the property right more complicated including into it such an element as international recognition of a state. This provides the possibility of using movable and immovable property and legal institution of judicial protection of owners' rights, same as entrenchment of extritoriality of the act of nationalization.

In terms of the declarative concept of recognition of a State, its international legal personality does not depend on other declaration of will of other states that excludes unconditionally the political nature of the process of nationalization filling it with economic and legal meaning only. At the same time the owner of property is deprived of the possibility to refer to judicial protection of movable and immovable property.

Analyzing the said above, we shall underline that in terms of the subject being studied the political problem of recognition of a state by the international community is secondary. From the legal point of view, presuppositions of own statehood of a certain territorial entity is essential; which means the availability of legal characteristics of a State. We would like to state that this is the starting point for the process of recognition of a State as a subject of international law.

In this regard it shall be mentioned that a State as a legal phenomenon is the unity of three elements: 1) ethnos; 2) territory; 3) state power. As regards the nature of the first element, (ethnos) V.A. Chertvenin was right to define it as an indigenous community, which sets oneself against all other similar communities out of a sense of complementarity, a crucial contradistinction "us – them", "own – foreign". The sense of ethnic affiliation is a variety of systemic link between people, which reflects their objective unity. Natural segregation of ethnic groups entails formation of their social and cultural identity. The territorial element is linked with the first one. It is defined not as an actual territory within certain boundaries, but a geographical range of a certain ethnic community forming the state. The third element is conditioned by the previous two as formation of State power is ensured by expression of will of "public sovereignty" and government is manifestation of it¹². Thus, lack of elements of a State as described above excludes the very possibility of raising a question of forming a new state and its recognition.

The stated above has an important practical meaning within the context of the adoption of the Declaration of Independence of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol¹³ by the Supreme Council of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea, as well as further legal actions that have resulted in legal consequences in the form of nationalization of the property of Ukraine on its territory.

tween states in compliance with the UN Charter: Resolution (XXV) of the General Assembly of the UN № 2625 of October 24, 1970, http://zakon4.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_569/card2#Card.

¹¹ Lukashuk I.I., *International Law, General Part. Textbook*, Publishing house BEK, Moscow, 1997, p.315.

¹² Problems of the general theory of law and state. Textbook for institutions of higher education. Under the general editorship of the correspondent member of the RAS, PhD in Legal Sciences, Professor V.S. Nersesyants, Publishing Group NORMA-INFRA-M, Moscow, 1999, p.545-562.

¹³ On the Declaration of independence of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol: Decree of the Supreme Council of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea № 1727-6/14 of March, 112014, <http://www.crimea.gov.ru/act/11726>. On independence of Crimea: Decree of the State Council of the Republic of Crimea №1745-6/14 of March 17, 2014, <http://www.crimea.gov.ru/act/11748>.

2. Aspects of private law

Another aspect as viewing nationalization as a form of termination of property relationships has private legal nature. It is naturally conditioned by the first aspect as mentioned above. Nationalization as a method of termination of the proprietary right is the realization of the sovereignty of a State in its relationships with its constituent entities. International public law acknowledges that nationalization is a prerogative of domestic jurisdiction of a state as it has no possibility to regulate legal relationships between the state and legal entities and physical bodies. This principle of non-intervention into domestic jurisdiction of a sovereign State has got confirmation in the jurisprudence of the International Court of Justice in case of UK against Iran (Consultative resolution of the International Court of Justice on Anglo-Iranian Oil Company in 1952) and further jurisprudence. Understanding this principle means that a sovereign State establishes independently legal mechanisms of termination of the proprietary right to the property located on its territory¹⁴. On the international level, only its legal outlining is possible.

In the studied aspect, the legal phenomenon of "nationalization" shall be seen in the narrow sense as an act of law enforcement, and in the broad sense as a legal mechanism aimed at evoking certain consequences in the form of termination of the proprietary right, which element, among others, is the number of legal facts. In the narrow sense, nationalization is an act of law-making of the State that establishes the ownership right of itself to the property of another subject of civil law. That means that the act of nationalization of property is a legal fact (action) resulting in consequences in the form of termination of an owner's proprietary right to property. This legal fact has the form of a legal act of a subject of public law. Taking into account the said above, an important role in the characterization of an act of nationalization as a law-making act of the State is played by the jurisdiction of the body adopting a respective legal act, the form of its entrenchment, as well as its individual-legal or regulatory-legal nature. Such a legal fact is a part of a set of facts establishing the mechanism of the termination of the property right.

Nationalization in the narrow sense as a legal fact has its backbone meaning along with other similar facts within the context of arising consequences conditioned by its legal goal – the establishment of the proprietary right of the State. Other similar legal facts are obligatory at nationalization as well, however, they do not have a legal meaning of their own for it. Moreover, the creation of a new

subject of international law is a legal fact influencing the process of nationalization of property and may work as a trigger for it.

An act of nationalization has a dual character of its legal action. It is aimed at achieving two results opposite by their nature: the termination of a right and the arising of a right. Characteristic to the legal fact under study is that in terms of time first an act of a right-terminating party appears, and only then, after a certain period of time, an act of a title-establishing one. At the same time, a right-terminating party to a legal fact stimulates formation of the title-establishing one, rather than another way around. So, at first the title of a person to certain property is terminated, and then the same title to the identified object arises, reappears in another form. And even if such period of time is short, still the right-terminating property of such legal fact is manifested before the title-establishing one, therefore it is more powerful as without its manifestation the title-establishing one cannot be exercised. The right-terminating aspect of this legal fact may be called a regressive one, and the title-establishing aspect – a progressive one as the latter is faced forward.

In a broader sense, nationalization is a series of steps by right enforcement subjects owing to which transfer of the proprietary right from a person to the state is carried out. Such a broad understanding of nationalization presupposes certain stages and procedures by which legal consequence is achieved in the form of arising of the proprietary right of the state to property belonging to another subject.

3. Legal conditions of nationalization

Thus, considering nationalization within the context of mechanism of termination of the property right it is necessary to distinguish such elements of it:

1) *existence of international -legal conditions for nationalization*. This legal fact provides for founding a new state as a result of public and political transformations;

2) *adoption of a regulatory and legal act by an authorized public authority*. It is made by way of establishing a public authority with respective powers and adopting by it a resolution in the legal procedural way;

3) *making reasonable compensation for the cost of nationalized property* – provides for unconditional compensation of the cost of the expropriated property to its owner. This is a sign of efficient legal protection of the property interest of a subject of law as stipulated in international sources of law;

4) *carrying out state registration of proprietary rights of the state to such property* – as legal

¹⁴<http://www.icj-cij.org/homepage/ru/summary.php>.

recognition of transition of the proprietary right to property.

Some scientists underlined additional legal facts in the set of facts underlying nationalization, for example, voluntary transfer, or court judgment¹⁵. However, such a view evokes reasonable scientific rejection. The meaning of voluntary transfer as a legal fact at nationalization of property as an element of its set of facts has no legal sense. Expression or failure to express his own will by the owner does not influence the arising of consequences in the form of his title termination. The act of nationalization is the will of the State conditioned exclusively by the principle of reasonable compensation for the cost of nationalized property. Otherwise, the act of nationalization will turn into a public offer resulting in changes in the legal nature of expropriation in general.

Taking into account the legal nature of expropriation, the role of a court judgment is reduced as it duplicates regulatory direction of the State backed by own enforcement. We understand that the author makes efforts to protect as effectively as possible rights of the owner of property being nationalized by creating the probability of a pre-judicial as well as a judicial settlement of this issue. Very possibly, this includes taking into account procedural tactics of establishing to satisfaction of court the expediency of nationalization, reasonableness of the choice of property subject to privatization, and the amount of reasonable compensation for its forced alienation. But we believe that the supporters of this approach did not fully take into account the political conditions under which nationalization is carried out. It results in the objective impossibility of efficient judicial protection of rights of the owner with national legal tools on the principle of "nemo iudex in sua causa".

4. *Summing up*, it can be stated that the above-mentioned stages of nationalization are independent legal facts, which, due to their accrual, form a set of facts, the legal consequence of which is termination of the proprietary right of a person and arising of the same proprietary right of the state. This set of facts shall be classified as interlinked (rigid) one as within its system there is a clear dependence of one legal fact on another (previous one). They accrue in strict sequence. Lack of one of the above-listed elements in the set of facts brings to its defectiveness. In its turn, such defectiveness makes impossible arising of consequences "programmed" by the legal model of nationalization in the disposition of the respective norm of law.

II. Particular aspects of nationalization acts in the temporarily occupied territory of Ukraine - Crimea

Within the context of the temporary occupation of Crimea, one of the most important practical issues with regard to nationalization is the problem of protection of defining the amount of compensation to be paid to the owner by the State at nationalization of property, and the formation of efficient mechanisms of protection of proprietary rights at nationalization of property by the government of a non-recognized State, including in case of its further cession to another subject of international law.

Firstly, the legal viability of the Republic of Crimea and SSC Sevastopol shall be contemplated through time, from the moment of conventional secession from Ukraine (March 17, 2014) till the time of conventional admittance to the Russian Federation as new constituent entities (March 18, 2014), and from the moment of such conventional admittance to present time.

At the *first stage* of legal existence of the Republic of Crimea and SSC Sevastopol, a Decree of the State Council of the Republic of Crimea № 1757-6/14 of March 17, 2014 "On nationalization of enterprises and property of sea transport of the sphere of management of the Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine and the Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine located in the territory of the Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol"¹⁶ was adopted containing the termination of the proprietary right of the state of Ukraine in respect to 15 property items.

As regards the *second stage*, we shall state that on March 18, 2014 the Agreement between the Russian Federation and the Republic of Crimea was concluded for admitting the Republic of Crimea to the Russian Federation and creation of new constituent entities of the Russian Federation¹⁷ (hereinafter – the Agreement), which de facto has formed a legal

¹⁶ On nationalization of enterprises and property of sea transport of the sphere of management of the Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine and the Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine located in the territory of the Republic of Crimea and city of Sevastopol: Decree of the State Council of the Republic of Crimea № 1757-6/14 of March 17, 2014. <http://www.rada.crimea.ua/ua/act/1761>

¹⁷ Agreement between the Russian Federation and the Republic of Crimea for admitting the Republic of Crimea to the Russian Federation and creation of new constituent entities of the Russian Federation of March 18, 2014. http://press.ua/mainmedial/tekst_dogovoru_pro_prynyatiya_krymu_u_rossijsk_u_federatsiyu_55014.html

¹⁵ Zhabreyev V.V., Creation of proprietary rights to real estate property. *Diss.* SHEI Urals State Law Academy, 2005, p. 166-167.

framework for the Russian Federation as regards legal relationships that have arisen in view of it and after its conclusion.

It allows us to state that the Russian Federation has *de jure* recognized the universal legal succession of rights and obligations in respect to the nationalized immovable/movable property located in the territory the Republic of Crimea and SSC Sevastopol within the period of conventional state independence in compliance with Article 17 of the Vienna Convention on legal succession of states in respect to state property, state archives and state debts of 8 April 1983¹⁸. On the other hand, since March 18, 2014 it has established a legal procedure of nationalization of property in the Russian Federation specifically in the Republic of Crimea and SSC Sevastopol in compliance with Article 235 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation¹⁹ (hereinafter – CC of the RF). Article 235 CC of the RF states that transfer of property belonging to citizens and legal entities into state property (nationalization) is carried out on the grounds of federal law with compensation for the cost of such property and other damages as envisaged by Article 306 CC of the RF. Infringement of this regulation gives the right to vindication of the property vindication under Article 301 CC of the RF.

Thus, we have established that the subject of recovery of damages and other amounts, same as the subject of vindication at the adoption of an act of nationalization within the period of March 17, 2014 – March 18, 2014 is the Russian Federation, and after concluding the Agreement – a respective subject of unlawful actions – the State Council of the Republic of Crimea, the Legislative Assembly of Sevastopol.

From a legal point of view, it is expedient to refer to the respective court of the Russian Federation with a request to acknowledge the legal act as invalid or impose vindication requirements upon a public authority of the Russian Federation acting in the temporarily occupied territory.

To substantiate the legal position chosen, it shall be mentioned that the logic of a lawmaker of Ukraine in this regard differs greatly from generally accepted approaches in the theory of civil law to formation of effective methods of civil rights protection. The adoption of the Law of Ukraine № 1207-VII "On protection of rights and freedoms citizens and legal regulation in the temporarily

occupied territory of Ukraine"²⁰ (hereinafter – the LU № 1207) of April 15, 2014 shall help to resolve a number of issues related to protection of proprietary rights of physical bodies and legal entities, however, a thorough analysis of its provisions allows making an opposite conclusion.

In accordance with Article 11 of the LU № 1207, acquiring and termination of the proprietary right to real estate property located in the temporarily occupied territory shall be performed in compliance with laws of Ukraine outside the temporarily occupied territory. With this, any legal act made in respect to real estate property, including land plots, in the temporarily occupied territory in violation of requirements of Article 11 of the LU № 1207 shall be deemed invalid from the moment of making it and shall not have any legal consequences, save for those related to its invalidity. Land and its subsoil, air, water and other natural resources within the boundaries of the territory of Ukraine, natural resources of its continental shelf, exclusive (sea) economic zone, which are the objects of the proprietary right of Ukrainian people, military property, property of state authorities and state enterprises, institutions and organizations situated in the temporarily occupied territory and being the property of the state of Ukraine, cannot be transferred into ownership of other states, legal entities or physical bodies in any other way, save as provided for by laws of Ukraine.

With this, Ukraine, in compliance with provisions of the LU № 1207, assumes political and legal obligations with the aim of the protection of peace, safety, rights, freedoms and lawful interests of citizens of Ukraine residing in the temporarily occupied territory, as well as lawful interests of the state of Ukraine. Besides, Article 17 states that Ukraine undertakes to make all and any efforts as stipulated in the Constitution and laws of Ukraine, norms of international law, to free the territory Ukraine from occupation as soon as possible, restoration of integrity and sovereignty of the state, restoration of humans rights and freedoms of citizens violated in view of occupation in the entire territory of Ukraine.

The same provision is contained in the Law of Ukraine № 1636-VII "On establishing a free trade zone "Crimea" and peculiar features of carrying our economic activities in the temporarily occupied

¹⁸ Vienna Convention on legal succession of states in respect to state property, state archives and state debts of 08 April 1983.
http://zakon1.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_072.

¹⁹ Civil Code of the Russian Federation.
<http://www.consultant.ru/popular/gkrf/>.

²⁰ On protection of rights and freedoms of citizens and legal regulation in the temporarily occupied territory of Ukraine: the Law of Ukraine of April 15, 2014 № 1207-VII, <http://zakon1.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1207-18/page>.

Kostruba: Nationalization of real estate property

territory of Ukraine"²¹ of August 12, 2014 (hereinafter - the LU № 1636). In accordance with Article 8 of this law, Ukraine guarantees the protection of proprietary and non-proprietary rights of natural persons and legal entities in the territory of free trade zone "Crimea" in accordance with the laws of Ukraine, including the protection of foreign investments.

However, economic instruments able to secure these state guarantees of Ukraine are not established by other legal regulatory acts, namely the Law of Ukraine №719-VII "On state budget of Ukraine for the year 2014"²² of January 16, 2014. Unfortunately, this allows to speak about politically motivated declarations that have nothing to do with an actual and effective protection of proprietary rights of people.

Besides, the invalidity of activities of officials, authorities created in the temporarily occupied territory fixed by law hinders Ukrainian institutions from carrying out reasonable judicial procedures as established by national procedural law with their participation. The change of the territorial jurisdiction of disputes related to real estate excludes as well the possibility of enforcement of court judgments adopted by Ukrainian courts in the temporarily occupied territory.

That is why when resolving issues of proprietary rights protection in connection with nationalization of property, it would make sense to apply legal tools on the principle of "reverse procedural activity", which means applying procedural methods of proprietary rights protection stipulated by the national laws of the occupier State.

²¹ On establishing a free trade zone "Crimea" and peculiar features of carrying our economic activities in the temporarily occupied territory of Ukraine. Law of Ukraine of August 12, 2014 №1636-VII, <http://zakon1.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1636-18>.

²² On the State budget of Ukraine for the year 2014 the Law of Ukraine of January 16, 2014 №719-VII, <http://zakon1.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/719-18>.